
Militarism as an Ethnic Tool to Gaining Political Power in Nigeria

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Abstract

In 1914, the British imperialist, consummated an unholy marriage between the Southern and Northern Protectorate, the union became the Nation of Nigeria. Prior to the amalgamation, the two Protectorates have been ruled apart, and thus were not fully prepared for the long term political, economic and social relationship being imposed on them by the imperialists in 1960 when Nigeria gained independence. At that time, the colonial officials tended to favour the extension of the European education and modern services first. In the North, such was forbidden because of very strong Islamic culture of the people. In effect, when the colonial office decided to amalgamate the Northern and Southern Protectorates into a single political unit, the two regions were already on very different Paths. The bad blood generated by the forced amalgamation has continued to hunt the Nation in every strata of her development. Until recently the Nigerian Political landscape has been ravaged by constant military intervention .On each occasion, the military boys have often hinged their intervention on the need to root the country of bad and corrupt leaders without recourse to the effect of cultural differences of the people.

Moreover, since the first military coup of January 15, 1966 some ethnic groups in the country have observed military enrollments as means of consolidating Political power both in and out of Power. The subsequent ones have proved clear evidence to this assertion. The military is now polarized around ethnic and political blocks, ethnic consideration has diminished professionalism. As a result, the admission into military services is no longer on merit. In that sense, the professionalism has been compromised. We now have military that is ill prepared

psychologically to protect the territorial boundary of the country. Nigeria as a Nation is still groping through the process of Nationhood, and at the same time faced with insecurity challenges that the military could not contend. Morale is low even as Sense of patriotism is lacking among the military. In this paper, attempt has been made to highlight the reasons why the military has failed in her responsibilities in Nigeria, and solution proffered on how best to reposition the Military for effective National service.

KEYWORDS: Military intervention, Decree, Caliphate, Esprit de corp. and Cabal.

INTRODUCTION.

Nigerian Politics has become more of the application of physical tussle, the appellation of ‘do or die’ and the formation of formidable clique to recycle political leadership. It seemingly has relegated the adoption of the ideas of using political ideology to win the electorates votes. Obviously the politicians in Nigeria have come to realize that the quickest mean to gaining political power is through might. The adoption of money bag approach termed to have become very important instrument to retain power. The danger this portends is that the alliance with military and Para-military organs is as good as securing victory by hook and crook by the political cabal or gladiators. The judiciary has become addition to the shenanigan.

Military intervention to Nigerian political terrain in the 1960s ushered an era to subsequent interferences that adversely influenced the development of the democratic government, and thus have laid the political foundation and equation of Nigeria by creating space for both the serving and highly influential retired military officer in Nigerian political terrain. The power of using the military to change government has not only opened the eyes of the masses, but likely has opened the eyes of the army to notice an avenue to access easy political power. It has also been noticed that the need to consolidate the source to power, has affected a kind of compromise to military professionalism, Measures have been taken to promote more intake of particular ethnic group to join officer cadre of army officers training school, far more than the others. This act has given such ethnic group an edge over the other groups’. The bad blood generated as a result has influenced negative the ‘esprit de corps’ of the military.

Military intervention in Nigeria is now seen a medium to not only balance power but to perpetuate the political domination of a particular ethnic group. This act has continued to undermine political cohesion of the Country. Nigeria can only grow when the military become conscious of their primary responsibilities .When merit is enthroned in every aspect of the peoples live.

A BRIEF HISTORY OF NIGERIAN MILITARY.

First and foremost, military services are very essential in the course of nation building. As a matter of fact, the military safe guide law and order by enforcement, and thus provides the needed intervention under the law required to protect group’s sovereignty. Military formation in Niger-area history goes beyond the imagination of some scholars. In other words, Nigerian military services took formation during the era of the abolition of slave trade, at the time when services of able men were needed to stop slave trade by the British abolitionist. Asiegbu, aptly captured the view when he stated, thus, ‘the development of British military institutions or activities in west Africa could be traced back to the early 19th century, beginning with the anti-slave trade naval squadron of the British navy which operated along west Africa coastal waters intercepting slave vessels’. The military formed and deployed during that period was done to protect the Economic interest of the British over her West

African territory. However, the fact remains; they operated in African soil and as such could be counted for Africa military formation. In effect, the activities of this early military formation and engagement started from 1808 when the abolition took effect, till 1860s, when Lagos became the crown colony.

Apart from the anti-slavery squad, there were various constabulary forces established in different locations of West Africa. Some of them engaged in dual responsibilities of police and military duties. ‘In the Lagos colony Captain John Glover, as administrator of the colony created, between 1861 and 1862 the famous Hausa militia which became the nucleus of the Lagos constabulary’.

In 1895, the Lagos militia split into two, with one becoming a civil police and the other a military unit. The most people recruited into the militia came from the liberated African and run away domestic slaves. During this time too, the Royal Niger Constabulary (RNC) has come into existence. The Royal Niger Company formed the Constabulary solely to protect its trade within the coast and the hinterland from undue interferences.

In effect, the Royal Niger Company continued to maintain the Royal Niger Constabulary until 1897, when the West Africa frontier force (WAFF) was formed. ‘The WAFF originated in 1897 as an organized military machine for the imperialist subjugation of West African peoples and kingdom’. The West African Frontier Force was therefore formed to replace the ineffective Royal Niger Constabulary. As the name implied, WAFF continued to offer military services to the British Colonial government .It was however, Lord Fredrick Lugard that gave WAFF the needed bite when he arrived Lokoja to assume the position of the first Commissioner and Commandant of the West African Frontier Force. On arrival he pursued a vigorous recruitment policy both in Yoruba land and in the Benue, and other districts of Northern Nigeria’ ⁶.

The Diagram below aptly captured the transformation of the Glover’s Hausa Militia that metamorphosed to the Nigerian Army.

S/N	MILITARY FORMATION	YEAR OF FORMED AND OPERATION
1	Glover’s Hausa Militia	1862-1863
2	Royal Niger Constabularies	1863-1893
3	Niger Coast Oil Rivers Irregular	1893-1900
4	Lagos / Calabar Battalion	1900
5	1 st and 2 nd Northern Regiment	1901-1902
6	3 rd Northern Nigerian Regiment	1903
7	1 st and 2 nd Southern Nigerian Regiment	1905
8	Southern Nigerian Regiment	1911
9	Nigerian Regiment	1914

All these formations existed and operated within the specific time frame until 1956 when the Queen’s own Nigerian Regiment was formed. In 1959, QONR changed to the Royal Nigerian Military force and in 1960 the Royal Nigerian Army (RNA) was formed. When Nigeria became federal Republic in 1963, the Army adopted full control and thus became Nigerian Army (NA). From 1963 the Nigerian Army had emerged to have Air force and Navy, this is in addition to other Para-military organizations in Nigeria.

THE GENESIS OF ETHNIC POLITICS IN NIGERIAN MILITARY.

The seed of discord in Nigerian Military could trace to the Colonial era. Although during that time the British Colonial Administrators focused their attention on building the Army based on certain factor, and that was warfare experience. On that note, it should be recalled that when the Colonial government contemplated building the Military the criteria was emphasized by Asiegbu, thus, 'Lugard adopted a policy of keeping the entire force predominantly Hausa, with Yoruba as the next preferred ethnic group to recruit into the force'. Fredrick Lugard took the above decision perhaps due to the fact that when the Europeans arrived Niger area, they were confronted with Yoruba groups that have been fighting for years firstly among themselves and secondly against the British interlopers. Dexterity exhibited could have informed the Colonists to have them recruited into the National Army. Again with the Hausa /Fulani they just wedged religious wars and have also confronted the British Colonial Administrators, this too, could have informed the Colonists to consider them fit enough to be recruited into the Army. From the forgone, it could be affirmed that such formed the basis of initial recruitment.

In addition, Ukpabi in Asiegbu, had supported to say, thus, 'Most British officials in the late 19th century regarded the Mohammedan Hausa as possessing by far the best soldierly qualities'. Again this position was enhanced due to readily availability of Horse, the Cattle and Carmel which was very useful in transportation and warfare. In that respect, the moment the British Colonial Administrators began to make preferences on ethnic consideration for recruitment into the National Army, the moment the seeds of ethnicity in recruitment were sown. The danger this portend was that when Nigeria gained independence there was serious imbalance in the Military, this is a bitter truth.

From 1950s to 1960s when the interest of other ethnic groups became noticeable political crises started. The crisis led to the first Military coup of 15th January 1966. Deliberately the coup was tagged Igbo coup for the sake of perpetuating an agenda of a group control of the Army. In other words, the growing number of people enlistment in the Army outside the traditional base aroused mistrust and hatred among the Hausa/Fulani people in particular. So when Gen. Aguiyi Ironsi an Igbo Army officer became the Head of State after the first Military coup the venom of the North the base of the Hausa, Fulani etc was let loose. The targeted killing of Igbo Soldiers laid credence to the ethnic sentiment in the Army. By implementing targeted attacks on Igbo army officers, the North aspired to reduce the number of Igbo in the army and psychologically to reduce their interest in enlistment. In fact, prior to the June 29th 1966 counter coup that resulted to Igbo massacre which led to the civil war, the North in collaboration with one of the major ethnic group the Yoruba has succeeding in planting discord in the polity.

For instance, in Aburi Ghana where Nigerian leaders have gone to deliberate on how to restore peace by proffering solutions on how to stop the targeted killing, 'contrary to the decisions at Aburi recruitment into the Army has continued in different parts of the Country except the East'. This further aggravated the situation, even as 'Northern Soldiers with the aid of civilian massacred thousands of Eastern Nigerians in the North and some even in Lagos,' the Army partisanship was not hidden. These unprovoked attacks further heightened and dampened the Esprit De corp. in the Army. By mortgaging the spirit of Equity, justice was thrown overboard.

This violation became apparent when Lt. Col. Yakubu Gowon the leader of Nigeria failed to honor the resolutions taken after the Aburi meeting .As if that was not enough, within the

time of the Aburi meeting ‘armed soldiers of Northern origin from Ibadan raided Benin Prison and removed soldiers who had been detained as a result of their alleged involvement in the attempted coup of 15th January 1966. The Northerners among the detainees were set free and repatriated to the North, the remainder mainly Easterners were murdered under brutal circumstances’. This was the extent to which Ethnicity was hoisted in the Military. Orjiakor laid credence to this deliberate attempt at sustaining the promotion of Northern dominance of the Military, when she stated thus, ‘the Igbo have been consistently sidelined in the recruitment of soldiers in the Nigerian army, navy and air force’.

THE NIGERIAN MILITARY AS AN INSTRUMENT OF GAINING ETHNIC POLITICAL POWER IN NIGERIA.

Ethnic Politics is very strong in Nigeria because unifying factors have been mortgaged by the British Colonists who created the Country. The policy of divide and rule initiated by the British underscored the foundation of Political unity among the diverse groups that would subsequently collapse into a Nation. By applying force to install puppet warrant chiefs in Nigeria, the people of Nigeria were taught the easiest way to gain Political power by the British government. The amalgamation of groups from diverse cultural divides into a Nation seriously created problems on leadership. The consequence of that challenge was the fight for the control of the military machinery in an attempt to permanently operate within the corridor of Political power. This marked the genesis of the ethnic contest over the control of the military for the sake exercising political authority within and without.

The above tendency incubated the enthronement of mediocrity over merit in the military. The danger it portend was that, within 20 years after Nigeria has gained Political independence from the British it has experienced over six military coups. In effect, the absence of commitment to national course denied the common people of Nigeria the opportunity to understand genuinely the meaning of selflessness in national service.

Ethnic instigated tussles for power have resulted to the Nigerian civil war of 1966-1970 with the casualty being one of the major groups the Igbo. Because of the success of most of the military coups in Nigeria, enlistment at the officer cadre has been made easier for certain groups, while others have been subjected to strenuous screening. Before the Biafran war, the second military coup carried out by the Fulani in collaboration with their Northern Nigerian surrogates ended up to usher ethnicity in the military. Through the second coup of 29th June 1966, ‘esprit de corps’ died in Nigerian military. It also opened the eyes of the ethnic groups to the strength of the military toward ascending to Political control of Nigeria. Military in Nigerian Politics also killed the Democratic values which Nigeria has consistently aspired to install.

From the time of Political independence in Nigeria, till date, Nigeria has experienced over ten military coups with greater of them being successful. From the records almost all the botched coups were carried out by soldiers from the minor ethnic groups. This observation lays credence to the strength of effective ethnic control of the military to Political control in Nigeria. In effect, In spite of recent decline at the level of military intervention in Nigeria Politics, Handelmann has observed, thus, ‘In a number of Countries such as Nigeria and Syria, the armed forces remain powerful force in Politics’. The implication of the foregone assertion, is that, though the military of recently have withdrawn from Politics, they have however remained a formidable power brokers, having direct input in selecting the Political leaders in even Democratic setting in Nigeria.

Again, military intervention and the Promotion or as a medium towards the Promotion of ethnic agenda could be aided by the nature of the Nation's internal Political structure. In addition to that, the inability to take the education and training of the military officers serious has greatly influenced their Political values, Huntington in Handelman argued, thus, 'a country wishing to keep the military out of Politics must impact professional values to the officers'. This value tend to be lacking in Nigeria because the challenges facing Nigeria is internally induced as to attract the attention of the military in meddling in domestic affairs including Politics. So 'by engaging the military or teaching officers to deal with internal security threats involved them in the study of domestic Political and Economic issues'. This is the major reason why the incidence of military coups tend to have been recorded more in developing Countries .Again, groups that is always at war over contention to seek commanding control of others in a given geographical space may likely attempt to hijack the instrumentality of power, the Military to control others.

From the work of Chinweizu, the deliberate attempt to hoist ethnic control of the army; have been exposed. In that respect, Chinweizu was accredited to have said in his work, in Omoruyi's interview with Babangida, the military Head of State when the transition to democratic government was truncated in June 12th 1993.Omoruyi was quoted to have said about Gen. Ibrahim Babangida, thus, 'when it was clear that the President was serious with the transition programme, and it seemed to them that he was actually thinking of handing over power they(the North) initiated the removal of Chief Olu Falae from the office of the secretary to Federal Military Government and appointed a Fulani'. From the above account it was obvious that ethnic Politics was active within and without the government.

THE NIGERIAN MILITARY AND NATION BUILDING.

The activities of Nigerian military as it has to do with politics are well documented. Nigerian Military's deviation from their core responsibilities has adversely affected their contributions to the process of nation building. This is evidently because successive military coup in Nigeria usually set the tone for momentary disruption of democratic rule the panacea for nation building.

Nwabughuogu in his book, succinctly stated, the danger inherent in military intervention in African Politics thus, 'this is by far, the major cause of instability in Africa. It differs from the other stabilizing agents, in the sense that a successful military intervention overthrows the existing government and completely disrupts the system'.

In Nigeria national service has attracted ethnic interest. This interest is borne due to the general belief among the groups, that whoever controls the authority of national service controls the nation. This informed the infiltration of ethnicity tendency in the military by retired military officers notably from the Hausa/ Fulani stocks, who have continued to show remarkable interest in military echelon even during civilian governments. Some of them though out of politics have secured their relevance by accepting being appointed traditional leaders as to enable them to remain in the corridor of power. One of such persons was retired Major Mustapha Jokolo the former Emir of Gwandu. This retired officer is credited to have been the very man who, 'at a meeting of Emirs in March 2005, called for a fight with Obasanjo government'. The aim of the fight called for by Major Jokolo retired was to install a Fulani President or a puppet. It should be recalled Obasanjo was elected democratically, the call for removal was due he was not a Fulani. Considering the office of the Emir of Gwandu, the second after the Sultan of Sokoto, one would understand the extent to which the military in Nigeria has been polarized.

Again in a book 'African Politics' edited by Emezie, C.A. and Ndoh, C.A. Okereke Okechukwu in his paper, has pointed out the danger portend by the Military in the course of Nation building when he stated, thus, 'military coups terminated the new democracies in Africa before it took root, frequent military coups have retarded the political and economic progress of Africa'.

From the above account, it is imperative to say that most military coups in Africa has its root course to ethnic motives, beside, it happened mostly at the time when most African nations, having gained political independence from the colonists, needed more time to deepen the newly acquired democratic values. In that regard, the supportive roles needed from the military towards building enduring democratic principles, was over taken by ethnic politics, instigated through constant military coups. Regrettably, the 'professionalistic Values as discipline, command structure, nationalism and sacrificial spirit noted with the military died in Nigeria when ethnicity crept into the command structure too. In fact, in the course of the fall out after the second military coup in Nigeria, Lt. Col. Ojukwu has refused to acknowledge Lt. Col. Yakubu Gowon as the new Head of States when Gen. Aguiyi Ironsi was assassinated based on the fact that he was not the rightful person to take charge due to the presence of other senior officers. With regard to the above account, 'the military regimes in many African states have been a disaster. Instead of being corrective as they often claim or profess on taking power, they have ended up being the problem themselves'.

During the time of Col. Gowon as the Head of State in Nigeria, one would have expected him to exhibit the full military professionalism as to unify the country, but no tangible move was made to bring together the already divided country after the second military coup in Nigeria. Chinweizu aptly captured the new ethnic agenda that was promoted in his compilation, titled, 'Caliphate Colonialism: The taproot of the trouble with Nigeria. In that book, he had stated, thus, 'by 1999, the caliphate had evolved a peculiar federal system that allows them to dominate and exploit other Nigerians behind a façade of democracy'. It is therefore obvious to say that the military midwife the misrule that for years now beguiles Nigeria. So whatever positive contributions made by the military in Nigeria, has been made insignificant due to negative impacts it has created in the nation's political terrain. In order to sustain ethnicity in Nigeria politics by the military, Chinweizu has further stated, 'the military resorted to all manner of makeshift measures to hang on to power sometimes ruling through their members, and at other times through willing tools from the Northern minorities or loyal agents from the conquered south'.

From the records of the past leaders of Nigeria, the Igbo people, one of the major ethnic groups in Nigeria tend to have been deliberately denied the opportunity to rule the Country in military or as a civilian even when democratically elected to rule by Caliphate instigated politics. This is a clear indication of ethnicity in Nigerian politics. Caliphate control according to Chinweizu is a political arrangement under the control of Sultan of Sokoto, supported by prominent Islamic leaders and Emirs in Northern Nigeria.

The table beneath will suffice to sustain the truth.

THE PAST AND PRESENT CIVILIAN AND MILITARY LEADERS OF NIGERIA

S/N	NAME	PARTY	REGION	NO.YEARS RULED	REMARK
1	Sir Abubakar T. Belewa	NPC Alliance	North	9 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
2	Gen. Aguiyi Ironsi	Military	East	5 Months.	Non-Caliphate Protégée.
3	Gen. Yakubu Gowon	Military	North	9 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
4	Gen. Muritala Muhammed	Military	North	1 Year.	Backed by the Caliphate.
5	Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo	Military	West	3 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
6	Alhaji Shehu Shagari	Civilian (NPN)	North	4 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
7	Gen. Muhammadu Buhari	Military	North	2 years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
8	Gen. Ibrahim Babangida	Military	North	8 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate
9	Mr. Ernest Sheneko	Interim	West	3 Months.	Backed by the Caliphate.
10	Gen. Sani Abacha	Military	North	5 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
11	Gen. Abdulsalami Abubakar	Military	North	1 Year.	Backed by the Caliphate.
12	Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo Rtd	Civilian (PDP)	West	8 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
13	Alhaji Umaru Yar'Adua	Civilian (PDP)	North	3 Years.	Backed by the Caliphate.
14	Dr. Goodluck Jonathan	Civilian (PDP)	South	6 Years.	Non-Caliphate Protégée.
15	Gen. Muhammadu Buhari Rtd	Civilian (APC)	North	8 Years	Backed by the Caliphate.
16	Alhaji Bola A. Tinubu	Civilian (APC)	West	2 Years-	Backed by the Caliphate.

The table above aptly illustrate the impact of the military rule in Nigerian politics .Gen. Obasanjo and Buhari even after having served as military Head of State, came back to satisfy ethnic agenda. In the History of Nigeria politics, ethnic conspiracies have continued to undermine the selection and election of popular candidates from other ethnic for no justifiable reason other than hatred. On two occasions a Nigerian of Igbo extraction eminently qualified and popularly supported to lead the country have been denied the opportunity. This scenario was initiated in the counter coup of 29th June, 1966 by the military.

During the second republic of 1983, the elected civilian president Shagari was about handing over to his vice President Dr. Alex Ekwueme, the a more popular candidate that would have healed the wound of the civil war and perhaps return the nation to the path of nation building, when the military under Gen. Buhari struck to return the nation to the civilian rule. The military intervention at the time speaks volume on the negative impact of the military to the

course of nation building in Nigeria. The question that keeps ringing in our minds has been why is it that in spite of the numerous military interventions in Nigeria, civilians they overthrew seems not to have learnt any lesson? In the past why did they have to intervene in spite of their inability to resolve some of the challenging Political problems in Nigeria?

Military intervention obviously has not resolved any Political problems created by the politicians. Considering the present political development in Nigeria, the Military has created synergy aimed at protecting the interest of the military whether in or out of power. The implication is that the military has compromised with the politicians by encouraging the option of always collaborating in election rigging. That is why it has become difficult now to intervene even when the democratic system in Nigeria has remained questionable.

Again, during the 2024 Presidential election Mr. Peter Obi was poised to win the election when ethnic conspiracy again reared its ugly head to truncate his election. During the election of 2024, it was obvious that Peter Obi lost the election not because people did not vote for him, but because the cabals inspired by ethnic politics saw him as a threat to a sustained system. And the electoral body succeeded in robbing him of the Presidential ticket with the backing of the military.

In addition, the military intervention obviously has not resolved the teething problems created by the civilian, as their motives were not always for national interest. This is because the successive civilian governments have not proved to have learnt anything. Rather the civilian government in Nigeria tends to have built strong collaborative link in politics with the military. In that regard, the military in recent times, tend to be contented with the civilian's political provisions and as such has been very supportive to successive civilian rules in Nigeria whether good or bad. Nwabughuogu aptly captured why the military shifted focus from serving the national interest, when they, 'saw political power as a means of grabbing enough resources to solve the financial problems of themselves and their families'. This also was in addition to the protection of ethnic agenda which has become a panacea to the assumption of the office of the Presidency in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION.

Several factors have been adduced as being responsible for the military intervention in African Politics by some scholars and public commentators. The Military on their own have continued to claim the basis of their intervention is to effect corrective measures often time made necessary by the corrupt politicians. This assertion has however been found not entirely true, considering the growing incidence of Ethnicity during each military regime in Nigeria. Nevertheless, the fact however remains; that the constant military intervention in African politics is determined by the level of political culture of the people. According to Fines in Nwabughuogu, such is further determined 'by strength or weakness of attachment to civilian institutions'. For instance, if people are politically enlightened and military highly professionalized the lower the tendency for the military intervention.

In the case of Nigeria, ethnic politics started even before the nation gained Political independence from the British. It was only accelerated after independence, with the fear of political and economic domination leading to fierce contest among the groups, more so, on who should control the central politics. The effect of the Ethnic Politics shifted to the military when it became obvious that the military could afford easy route to the attainment of political leadership. It was on that premise too, that the military began to withdraw from its constitutional responsibility to dabble into politics through coups that almost became a routine, within 20 years after the nation's independence.

On account of some scholars, they have opined that the military intervened through coup because the civilians were corrupt. They often time had equally accused them of promoting nepotism and lacked the drive to weld the numerous ethnic groups together. This accusation is also noticeable during each military regime in Nigeria. However, the extent to which the army has succeeded in accelerating the process of nation building which they often claimed as the reason for her intervention still need to be seen.

When the military in Nigeria embarked on State and Local government creations in Nigeria, they deliberately arrogated to itself a very serious constitutional matter. In that regard, all the states and local government councils created in Nigeria were down by the Military. In addition, when the states and local governments were created, it was done in such a way to favour certain ethnic group. With such bias, it further became obvious, that the Nigerian military lacked the sense of Nationalism needed to develop the course of Nation building. On the basis of such flagrant behavior in states creation, the act of Nation building was stalled, even as ethnicity continued to induce every policy thrust of the government.

Again constant military interference in Nigerian Politics has demystified the revered Profession, even as mounting heaps of corrupt acts in the Military has eroded peoples trust and confidence on its ability to protect and safe guide national interest. For the Military to regain its trust and confidence it must desist from the local Politics but rather support to nurture the development of strong political institution. Recruitment and Commission to the Military service must strictly be on merit. The Military Personnel should be educated enough to understand their indelible responsibilities in Nation building. For the Nation's Military to attain the status of symbol of unity certain prominent Indigenous leaders should be prevented from having undue interference in the appointment of officers for certain sensitive Military positions and the reservation of certain office to certain Ethnic group. Promotion must be on merit and the Military made to be more professional inclined.

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